

Citizen Science in Kenya's Freshwater Aquatic Ecosystems Research and Monitoring: Status, Challenges and Prospects

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Abstract:

Globally, scientists are increasingly engaging members of the public in research activities. Citizen science approaches are vital in freshwater ecosystems research, monitoring and public education. Citizen science provides an opportunity to engage public in natural ecosystems monitoring and public education, and is a less costly strategy for data collection. However, there are challenges that hinder application of citizen science in freshwater ecosystems monitoring and public education. The role of citizen science in freshwater ecosystems research, monitoring and public education is discussed. Additionally, the challenges and future prospects for citizen science in freshwater ecosystems studies are examined.

Keywords: Citizenship Science, Aquatic Ecosystems, Volunteers, Monitoring, Education, Kenya.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Citizen science refers to the practice of engaging members of the public in scientific research (Cohn, 2008; Vohland et al., 2021; Wu and Hsu, 2025). It involves a collaboration between trained researchers and inexperienced volunteers in scientific research activities. The volunteers are members of the public who decide to engage in data collection to aid in large research projects for the love of scientific research and betterment of their communities (Shah and Martinez, 2016; Sommerwill and Wehn, 2022).

Citizen science has been successfully applied in various scientific disciplines as a cost-effective strategy for gathering data on large spatio-temporal scales for monitoring and education purposes (Gurnell et al., 2019; Lopez et al., 2024). The term 'citizen science' was utilized as early as 1900 and an outstanding example of citizen science include the bird's migration assessment through the Audubon Christmas Bird Count in the USA which started in 1900 and continuous to date (Evan et al., 2023; Vickers et al., 2025). In the past few decades, social networks and technology have accelerated inter-connectivity among members of the public and scientists. For example, internet and smartphones have become vital platforms for citizen science projects and many websites and mobile phone applications have been devised for citizen science research projects (Newman et al., 2012; Howard et al., 2022). These platforms also create opportunities for the local communities to collaborate with researchers in scientific research and biodiversity monitoring (Ahern and Hughes, 2024).

Worldwide, citizen scientists are working together with researchers to assess freshwater ecosystems conditions on different spatial and temporal scales (Ramírez et al., 2023; Lopez et al., 2024). Citizen scientists are gathering data on invasive and endangered organisms (Wallace et al., 2021; Pocock et al., 2024), assessing freshwater ecosystems restoration, participating in freshwater ecosystems management decisions and contributing to the understanding of the impacts of freshwater ecosystems quality on human health (Huddart et al., 2016).

One major advantage of citizen science for researchers and environmental managers is its cost-effectiveness (George et al., 2021; Wu and Hsu, 2025). For example, around 1.3 million people participate in citizen science programs per year amounting to about 2.5 billion US dollars (Theobald et al., 2015). Such cost-effectiveness is particularly vital for research projects which are spatially and temporarily more extensive (Toomey and Domroese, 2013). Other advantages of engaging citizen scientists in scientific research include increased scientific literacy, public engagement and raising awareness about the problems that affect the community at large (Walker et al., 2021; Davis et al., 2023; Wu and Hsu, 2025).

Citizen science provides many opportunities for gathering of data and engagement of local communities in monitoring of freshwater ecosystems (Kelly-Quinn et al., 2023; Gönner et al., 2024). Citizen science engagement varies from crowd-sourced data collection (i.e., contributory research) to considerable engagement in analysis of data and

relaying of information (i.e., collaborative research) and thorough development of research projects (i.e., co-created research) (Senabre et al., 2018). In this article, the application of citizen science in freshwater ecosystems research, monitoring and public education is discussed. Additionally, the status, challenges and future prospects for citizen science in Kenya are discussed.

2. THE ROLE OF CITIZEN SCIENCE IN FRESHWATER ECOSYSTEMS MONITORING, RESEARCH AND PUBLIC EDUCATION

Assessment of the ecological conditions of freshwater ecosystems is vital because of the various goods and ecosystem services that they provide (Strayer and Dudgeon, 2010; Sousa et al., 2025). However, freshwater assessment efforts around the globe are scarce and under-financed (Cortelezzi and Paz, 2023; Bushnell and Park, 2025). Citizen science provides the possibility of engaging local communities in research projects covering large spatio-temporal scales at a sustainable cost (Tricarico, 2022). For example, in China at least 20 citizen science projects primarily related to freshwater ecosystems emerged between years 2005-2022 (Wu et al., 2022). Most of these projects are related to monitoring of biodiversity and enhancement of water quality. These projects involved stakeholders such as non-governmental organizations, educational institutions, companies and governments. A study conducted in Germany evaluated the ecological status of small agricultural streams with more than 900 citizen scientists in about 100 monitoring groups and showed that about 60% of the monitoring sites did not achieve a good ecological status in terms of the composition of macroinvertebrates and suggested high exposure to pesticides (Gönner et al., 2024). The data collected by citizen scientists was highly correlated with data collected by professionals, indicating a high degree of accuracy.

Citizen scientists also collect data on endangered, threatened and invasive species in freshwater ecosystems. For example, Chowdhury et al. (2023) evaluated the priority areas for conserving biodiversity in Bangladesh using citizen science data and found that about 290 species are threatened and about 770 species are non-threatened. Protected area coverage differed substantially among the organism groups and was lowest for freshwater fishes.

Invasive species have a negative effect on biodiversity and freshwater ecosystem functions. Citizen science is a vital approach for monitoring invasive alien species, providing datasets over large spatio-temporal scales, with citizen scientists generating information that supports management actions (Pocock et al., 2024). For example, citizen scientists evaluated the distribution of invasive freshwater turtles in Greece and provided the first recorded data for five turtle species (Kalaentzis et al., 2023). In a different study, Clusa et al. (2018) engaged citizen scientists in monitoring of invasive species in Iberian Rivers and found that more than 20% of citizen scientists were able to correctly name invasive species. Additionally, more than 70% of the citizen scientists were in favour of control of invasive species. Elsewhere, citizen scientists detected the first record of the

invasive red swamp crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*) in northern Idaho, United States. Subsequently, aquatic ecosystems management agencies were informed and initiated efforts to assess and remove the invasive species (Morton et al., 2023). In the United Kingdom, citizen scientists have also been engaged in monitoring water quality, mapping and controlling invasive species (Collins et al., 2023).

Citizen science also plays a key role in monitoring of restored freshwater ecosystems (Huddart et al., 2016). In the USA, Edwards et al. (2018) evaluated the role of citizen scientists in monitoring the effect of stream restoration on the stream macroinvertebrates and found that citizen science can generate vital data about ecological restoration. A different study conducted in India evaluated the effect of restoration on water quality and birds' diversity and found that the abundance and richness of birds around the lake increased after restoration efforts and that water quality improved within the aquatic ecosystem (Yardi et al., 2019).

Citizen science presents an opportunity for evaluating research objectives on different spatial and temporal scales by actively engaging the public in the research process through activities such as co-creation of research objectives, experiments, collection of samples, processing of data and dissemination (Senabre Hidalgo et al., 2021; Yevenes et al., 2022; Lopez et al., 2024). For example, Lopez et al. (2024) explains how engagement of citizen scientists for over 30 years have enabled collection of data in hundreds of lakes. Collecting data at such large spatio-temporal scales would have been logistically and financially difficult without active engagement of citizen scientists. The research provides guidelines for initiating and sustaining research projects involving citizen scientists over large spatio-temporal scales.

In Ontario, Canada, citizen scientists were engaged in collection and processing of samples on plastic pollution in the Ottawa River and several advantages such as ease of recruiting citizen scientists and minimal costs of collecting data over the more than 500 km covered by the river were noted. The study recommended future research projects to consider using established citizen science networks and conducting both field and laboratory experiments (Forrest et al., 2019). In India, citizen scientists were engaged in monitoring of lake water quality using secchi disks. A network of citizen scientists was initiated and involved students from universities and research institutes and other stakeholders such as non-governmental organizations, fishermen and local residents. The citizen scientists collected data using secchi disks and transmitted it via a mobile application. The study highlighted the potential for use of simple tools for generation of datasets over large spatio-temporal scales by research projects (George et al., 2021). Another study engaged citizen scientists in a research project aimed at monitoring the effect of pollution on macroinvertebrates diversity in a river in western Uganda. Citizen scientists were engaged in identification of study sites, collection and processing of macroinvertebrate samples. The citizen scientists were encouraged to provide feed back about their experiences during the research project. Assessment of macroinvertebrates provided vital information about the ecological status of the river and citizen scientists

expressed primarily positive sentiments, highlighting satisfaction, education and increased awareness about environmental matters (Nkurunungi et al., 2024).

Public education is one of the key aims of citizen science projects and is a fundamental tool for educators whose objective is to involve learners in significant research (D'Alessio et al., 2021; Louw and Sanford-Dolly, 2024). In the USA, citizen scientists (i.e., undergraduate students) evaluated water quality while undertaking undergraduate engineering courses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results obtained were consistent with those reported in the yearly drinking water quality reports from the area of study. Most of the citizen scientists agreed that the citizen science project provided a positive learning experience during a period when attending face-to-face classes was difficult (D'Alessio et al., 2021).

Citizen scientists (i.e., high school students) were engaged in river water quality assessment to determine if their involvement in scientific activities could be increased and whether they could generate high quality data. Results showed that student data was similar to data collected by professionals and that the project had implications in terms of increasing students' science engagement (Brown and Liu, 2024). Training of citizen scientists during monitoring of riverine ecosystems has been shown to increase accuracy in macroinvertebrate samples identifications, promote relationships between researchers and citizen scientists, enhance taxonomic knowledge and education and the quality of data collected (Louw and Sanford-Dolly, 2024; Nkurunungi et al., 2024).

2.1 Citizen science in freshwater ecosystems monitoring in Kenya

Application of citizen science in freshwater ecosystems research and monitoring has recently gained popularity in different areas of the world and is a cost-effective method for collecting data (Njue et al., 2019). It also has the potential to promote public education and provide background information that supports governance and management of freshwater resources. In Kenya, relatively few researchers have evaluated the role of citizen science in freshwater ecosystems monitoring and management. For example, Weeser et al. (2018) evaluated the quality and quantity of hydrological data generated by citizen scientists in the western region of Kenya and found that the hydrological data generated was of high quality and that citizen scientists regularly reported measurements for most of the study sites.

Another study developed a Citizen-based Index of Ecological Integrity (CIEI) for evaluating the environmental condition of stream ecosystems in the Lake Victoria Basin, Kenya, and found that the approach was useful in identifying the source and extent of impairment in running water ecosystems (Aura et al., 2021). A research project based in Sondu-Miriu River basin trained citizen scientists to evaluate turbidity and found that the data collected was related to data collected using automated stations, suggesting that the citizen science data was of high quality (Njue et al., 2021). Citizen scientists have also been engaged in monitoring the distribution and abundance of birds in freshwater lakes (e.g.,

Lake Victoria) and contributed significantly in their management and conservation (Nasirwa and Bennun, 2000).

2.2 Challenges of engaging citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems monitoring in Kenya

Limited funding challenges most research projects and citizen-based research projects are not an exception. Some costs associated with citizen-based research projects include salaries for project staff, travel, hosting and maintenance of datasets on stable and accessible websites, laboratory supplies and materials for outreach activities. Although obtaining financial support for research may not be easy in general, citizen-based research initiatives may be able to adopt creative strategies to deal with the challenges. For example, citizen-based research can obtain research funds through strategies such as crowd sourcing campaigns or sponsorship by corporate organizations.

Citizen science research projects typically recruit participants who have a formal education, with adequate time for data collection and funds to afford the necessary gadgets and equipment (Pocock et al., 2018; Mahmoudi et al., 2022). This presents a challenge for projects engaging citizen scientists from marginalized and remote Kenyan areas where access to formal education or necessary infrastructure, equipment and gadgets is limited. These challenges can be reduced by initiating a trusted relationship with local communities and choosing relevant and co-designed technologies that take into account local culture, skills and knowledge (Chiaravalloti et al., 2022). Engagement of local communities can also be enhanced by utilizing recruitment approaches that reach varied volunteer profiles and a high number of local citizen science coordinators (Requier et al., 2020).

Participants dropout can be a challenge affecting citizen science research projects because most volunteers may be working or studying and can only engage in data collection during their free time. This can be resolved by planning research activities when citizen scientists are not occupied with other obligations. Participants dropout can also be addressed by motivating volunteers through incentives and communication about research details. Clear communication concerning how the data will be utilized and why the data are so important can play a crucial role in incentivizing the citizen scientists. Other incentives aimed at enhancing citizen scientists' involvement and retention include prizes, co-authorship in scientific reports and papers and information nudges (Coppa et al., 2020; Diekert et al., 2023; Moshi et al., 2023).

Ensuring data quality in citizen-led research projects represents a challenge in monitoring of freshwater ecosystems (Lukyanenko et al., 2016). The quality and accuracy of data collected by citizen scientists may vary widely depending on reliability of sensing devices, adherence to standards of scientific practice and the level of difficulty of the tasks assigned to citizen scientists (Lukyanenko et al., 2016; Ekman and Weilenmann, 2021). The quality of data collected by citizen scientists can be enhanced through utilization of multiple measurements at the same study site, comparison of citizen-science data with

data collected by research experts and independent automatic equipment (Salk et al., 2022).

Citizen-science data can play a crucial role in addressing national and global issues, and especially in monitoring of the large number of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) targets and indicators which the local and national authorities may be poorly equipped to assess (Fraisl et al., 2020). However, a lack of legal and policy frameworks concerning the use of citizen science data may hinder its use in state monitoring and management plans of freshwater resources in Kenya. Several legal and policy frameworks on the utilization of citizen science data have been implemented and include the United States crowd-sourcing and citizen science Act, European Open Science Policy Agenda and action 8 of the European Union road-map to streamline environmental reporting (US Congress, 2016; European Commission, 2017; European Commission, 2019).

Coming up with a successful experimental design can be a considerable challenge for many citizen-based research projects. Research projects should be designed carefully to ensure collection of adequate sample sizes to avoid sampling bias (Conrad and Hilchey, 2011). Training of citizen scientists represents a challenge because some of the research projects may require specialized equipment and prior knowledge about the planned study, such as identification of organisms and operation of monitoring equipment. Training of new citizen scientists can require substantial time, training and purchase of equipment. Logistical issues such as transportation to the field or access to private land may act as hindrances to engagement of citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems research in Kenya. Additionally, it may be challenging to ensure that citizen science projects take into account issues such as safety, rights, privacy and confidentiality of volunteers, authorship and acknowledgment in scientific reports and papers (Resnik et al., 2015; Resnik, 2019)

2.3 Future prospects in engagement of citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems monitoring and research in Kenya

In future, enhancement of engagement of citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems monitoring will promote scientific understanding of freshwater ecosystems, local community understanding and cooperation in freshwater ecosystems research. There is need to devise citizen science projects that are cost effective and can aid in collection of data at different scales.

Large citizen science datasets will be vital in detection of environmental patterns at spatio-temporal scales that are much more difficult and expensive to achieve based on data collected by professional scientists. These datasets will provide an early warning system that enables environmental agencies to respond to environmental stressors, increasing efficiency of mitigation efforts and reducing environmental impacts.

There is need for enhancement of coordination and communication between researchers and organizations involved in citizen-based monitoring and data should be made freely available to research scientists by the custodians of citizen science programs. This will maximize the utilization of these data to inform freshwater ecosystems scientific

research. Online data collection platforms can enable citizen scientists to engage in research and provide data to citizen-based freshwater monitoring projects (Fraisl et al., 2022).

There is need to take an innovative approach to citizen science by coming up with collaborative partnerships among professionals in a wide range of scientific fields such as populations distribution, conservation, ecology, computer and geographical information scientists and public policy. The objective is to enhance data quality through recruitment, training and engagement of participants and to regulate data quality issues such as data variability among volunteers, specimen identification errors and biases in data collection (Fritz et al., 2019; Fraisl et al., 2022). Partnerships among professionals across different fields will also help shape the online platform to meet the needs of different audiences

Engagement of citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems monitoring will require meeting the needs of volunteer participants. For example, improving the technologies used for interacting with citizen science participants and maintaining current and user-friendly taxonomical identification keys and environmental monitoring equipment.

A policy regarding access to and use of citizen science data will enhance engagement of citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems monitoring. Such a policy can help to evaluate citizen science data usage trends and enhance proper attribution and acknowledgment for data providers (Disckinson et al., 2012).

It is vital to expand the range of activities typically involved in running of citizen-science programs to extend beyond collection of data to include other activities such as data analysis and delivery of results to a broad range of stakeholders.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Involving citizen scientists in freshwater ecosystems research, monitoring and public education provides an opportunity to engage with local communities and to collect data at a comparatively low cost. Additionally, engagement of local communities in freshwater ecosystems monitoring and research will not only enhance scientific understanding of freshwater ecosystems, but also has the prospects to improve local communities' comprehension and valuation of vulnerable freshwater ecosystems. However, there are challenges which hamper the engagement of citizen scientists in scientific research, such as participants drop out, training of new citizen scientists and lack of adequate funds. The challenges associated with citizen-based research projects needs to be addressed to enhance its utility in monitoring of freshwater ecosystems and public education in Kenya. There is need for policy and legislative frameworks to enhance utilization of citizen science data in state biomonitoring programmes.

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